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**LOCALIZATION APPROACH IN DIRECTORY
BASED CACHE COHERENCY AND ITS IMPACT ON
CACHE COHERENCY IMPLEMENTATION- STUDY.**

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ABSTRACT

Todays systems are designed with Multi Core Architecture. The idea behind this is to achieve high system throuput. Once the Processor clock speed reached its saturation, designers opted for having multiple cores. Each Core or Processor equipped with their own private cache memory. But under Chip Multiprocessor, where all the processor have access to shared memory, having respective cache memory will result with Cache Coherency Problem. In Directory Protocol, for each block of data there is a directory entry that contains a number of pointers. The important advantage of directory based protocols is that they scale much better than snoopy protocols. In addition to this it has the advantage of ability to exploit arbitrary point-to-point interconnects. But mean time it also has the overhead in terms of the storage and manipulation of directory state. Communication cost is one of the major issue which accounts for the performance of Directory based cache coherency systems. Having the directory maintained with local memory always gives better performance. This paper discus different Directory Based implementation, in terms of its locality and its implications on the systems.

Introduction

Todays systems are designed with Multi Core Architecture. The idea behind this is to achieve high system throughput. Once the Processor clock speed reached its saturation, designers opted for having multiple cores. Each Core or Processor equipped with their own private cache memory. A typical shared memory multiprocessor contains multiple levels of caches in the memory hierarchy. Each processor may read data and store it in its cache. This results in copies of the same data being present in different caches at the same time. In order to maintain the consistency, Cache Coherence Protocols have been imposed on such systems. Cache coherence protocols are classified based on the technique by which they implement as Snooping and Directory based protocols. In bus based multiprocessor systems, appropriate

coherence actions can be taken if coherence is detected. These are called snoopy protocols. The name snoopy comes from snoop, because each cache snoops bus transactions to watch memory transactions of other processors. Snoopy protocols require the use of a broadcast medium in the machine and hence apply only to small-scale bus-based multiprocessors. Here all the Cache Controllers will be connected to the common address bus and hence observe each memory access for both read and write by other processors. This type of protocol is most commonly used method in commercial multiprocessor. In Directory based protocols, a main directory is maintained containing information on shared data across processor caches. The directory works as a look-up table for each processor to identify coherence and consistency of data which is currently being updated. A directory-based protocol is a smart way of implementing cache consistency on an arbitrary interconnection network.

Directory Organization

Choosing the structure of the directory should be one of the criteria for getting good system performance in terms of achieving memory consistency. Directory organization defines the storage structures that make up the directory and the nature of the information stored in it. There are three major approaches in Directory Structure, like Limited Pointers Allocation and Dynamic Pointer Allocation Directories[1] , and Sparse Directory Schemes. These organizations provide good performance even though incurring some memory overheads in terms of pointer locations.

In a traditional directory structure called Censier/Feautrier organization, the directory maintains a vector of valid bits, one bit per processor, for each data block at main memory. With this structure, the resulting memory overhead is exponentially increases with number of processors and hence does not support for the systems with very large number of CPUs [9]. Furthermore, even if the memory overhead was reasonable in a large-scale machine, the large size of the valid bit vector will result with difficulties in implementation. So when such traditional directory organizations incur excessive memory overhead, other alternative methods needs to be explored. A general approach in this regard for reducing memory overhead is by either reducing the directory's length or the directory's width.

Limited Pointers Directories

In small-scale multiprocessors usually a few caches contain a given block of data whenever a write occurs. In such case, on a write operation, the data is invalidated in all except the one cache. The valid bit vector in traditional directories has only a few of its bits set. It is therefore more efficient to replace the vector with several pointers, which are $\log n$ bit fields that encode the unique identities of those caches containing the data block. This overhead is calculated by dividing the number of bits in a directory entry by the number of data bits represented by that entry. Here the memory overhead is directly proportional to the number of processors and the number of pointers in a directory entry, and inversely proportional to the number of bytes in a cache block. With this approach it is possible to have the directory

entry with at least three pointers for most large-scale systems, and keeping the memory overhead much lesser than traditional directory schemes[7]. With only a small number of pointers in each entry, it may happen that the directory entry run short for a given memory block. This occurs when a request due to a read miss arrives at memory and the directory finds no free pointers remaining in that entry to record this state. To handle this there are two basic strategies like broadcast scheme and no-broadcast scheme. In a broadcast scheme, a broadcast bit in the directory entry is set, indicating that the directory is no longer keeping track of the caches containing that data. When a processor eventually writes the data, the directory must resort to broadcasting an invalidation request to all caches. No-broadcast scheme insists that not more than k cached copies of a block of data may exist at any given time. Here k is the number of pointers in each directory entry. When a free pointer is needed and if it is not available, a pointer is randomly selected and freed by invalidating the data from that cache the pointer identifies. It has been found that limited pointers directories incur reasonable storage overhead, and its implementation is straightforward[7]. However, in these systems performance may not be optimal especially in large-scale machines.

Dynamic Pointer Allocation Directories

The another directory organization proposed is the dynamic pointer allocation method. This method takes advantage of the fact that most data blocks are shared at any given time by only a few caches, while a few blocks may be widely shared. Similar to the limited pointers directories, this directory scheme uses pointers that contain the unique identities of those caches containing the data. However, the number of pointers available in an entry is not fixed, and it is rather allocated on-the-fly from a pool of available pointers. When a pointer is no longer needed, it is returned to the pool.

Here the directory is containing a number of pointers, each paired with a link to form basic data structure - linked list of cache pointers. In addition, each block of main memory has an associated dirty bit, a link to a list of pointers allocated to the block, and an empty bit that indicates whether or not the block's list of pointers is empty. When the list is not empty, the last pointer links back to the main memory block, forming a circular list. At system start-up, a single linked list consisting of all the pointers is built. A special register known as the free list link is set to contain the address of the first pointer/link pair; this register is a link to the head of the free list. On a cache miss, a pointer is removed from the free list and added to the head of the list for the desired memory block. When permission to write a block is requested by a cache, the directory steps through the block's pointer list, sending invalidations to each cache on the list and returning the pointers to the head of the free list. The end of the list is reached when the end-of-list bit associated with each pointer/link pair is found to be set. The dynamic pointer allocation directory adds less storage to each data block than a standard limited pointers directory with several pointers per entry. With this method of directory, memory overhead to be considered is in terms of the dirty bits, empty bits, and head links. Since caches are growing larger with each new generation of systems, the length of the pointer/link store must also grow accordingly. Therefore, the directory overhead will rise over time, due

to increases in the width of the pointer list head link field. It has been found that with this scheme, even a increase in the size of the pointer/link store by a factor of 10 or higher results with only a modest overhead increase for a given cache line size[7]. The dynamic pointer allocation scheme therefore has resulted with good storage efficiency even in the presence of large caches. The pointer/link store would scale gracefully over the time. The number of pointers required on a node depends on the cache size. The number of pointers that can be provided will therefore scale at the same rate as the size of cache memories.

As in a limited pointers directory, here also it is possible to run short of free pointers. This occurs if a pointer is to be allocated from the free list but the free list is found to be empty. The action to take on such instance is to use some means to select a pointer and then free it by sending an invalidation to the cache identified by that pointer. The selection of the pointer can be on random basis using some hardware register. Since the address of the block is needed to send an invalidation message, the list beginning at the pointer indicated by the register must be traversed until the last pointer on the list is found. This address and the pointer can be used to send an invalidation, thereby freeing the pointer/link pair. An interesting effect occurs if caches are allowed to replace clean blocks without notifying the directory. Stale pointers indicating caches that no longer contain the data may accumulate in the pointer/link store. If they are not returned to the free list, these stale pointers could potentially occupy most of the pointers that would otherwise be free, perhaps causing the directory to run short of free pointers frequently. This is undesirable since processing a read miss which is the most frequent directory operation, will be considerably slower at the directory if no free pointers remain. So while not required for correctness, enhancing the protocol by having caches send replacement notifications to the appropriate directory when a clean block is replaced shell improve the system.

Sparse Directory Schemes

The sparse directories scheme is based on the following observation that at any point of time only a few memory can be resident in cache. Here usually cache size will be lesser than the memory size. Given that coherence protocol only needs sharing information for lines in the cache, most directory entries are empty or not used in most of the time. For example, 1MB cache with 1GB main memory leads to 99.9% waste of directory space. The basic idea of the method is to minimum the overhead of the empty entries in the directory. A typical way to achieve this is to leverage the link list structure. For details, we have a linked list for each memory block. All cache lines of the specified block, probably in different nodes, are organized as linked list through an additional previous/next pointer in the cache line. To find the head of each list, we can have a single head pointer per line in memory. A more practical alternative would be to simply maintain a small lookup table storing the head of the list for cached lines. The sparse directory scheme can reduce the space overhead dramatically. We have some additional pointers in each node's cache, of which the size is proportional to the cache size. And we have a small lookup table in memory. However data write applications,

we have to iterate through the list, which make the latency proportional to the number of sharers.

Reducing number of messages in Coherence Protocol

Another option where in the performance of Directory based cache coherence system that could be enhanced for optimization is in terms of minimising the network traffic in implementation. Here mainly we take in to considerations the request for a cache line from requesting node to its home node, and the way how home node is going to serve this request. Mainly there are 2 approaches for serving this kind of request, Intervention Forwarding and Request Forwarding.

While considering the case of a read miss on dirty block, in order to serve the request, first the requesting node has to send the request to Home node, and the Home node will forward the Owner node id to the requesting node. Later requesting node sends data request message to Owner node, and Owner reply's data to requesting node. Finally Data and directory update message has to be sent to Home node from the Owner node. Hence totally there will be 5 message needs to be exchanged in order to serve the request.

Intervention Forwarding

While considering the case of a read miss on dirty block, with Intervention Forwarding, first the request is sent to Home node, and the Home node will forward the Intervention Read message to the Owner node, the Owner node is going to reply with Data to Home node, and finally Home node will respond to Request node with Data. Hence totally 4 message sequence will be required to serve this particular request in this method.

Request Forwarding

While considering the case of a read miss on dirty block, with Request Forwarding, the request node will first send the request to Home node, and the Home node will send the request to send data to the requesting node. The Owner node is going to reply to Home node as well as the requesting node with Data in single message. Hence totally 3 message sequence will be required to serve this particular request in this method.

Localization Approach

Designers could opt for factorizing the database and see that local data is resident in the relevant node, would improve the performance of cache coherency in distributed scenario. As in the case of either Intervention Forwarding or Request Forwarding, the requesting node have to send initial request to Home Node. If the data is localized, and requesting node is happened to be the Home Node, the message exchanges would be minimized and ultimate performance would be improved to a great extent with total number of message needed is zero. Even in other case, where nodes are arranged in hierarchical fashion, Intervention

Forwarding or Request Forwarding will happen within a local zone and thus improve the overall system performance. Hence factorizing the database and residenting it in appropriate sites of a distributed application also will improve the overall system performance by implementing the cache coherency withy minimal number of message exchanges among different nodes like Home node, Owner node and Requesting nodes.

Fig: A typical hierarchical node structure of multi processor nodes

The figure shown depicts a typical hierarchical node structure in a multiprocessor systems that could have been found in a distributed environment. With this structure the root node “a”, to be considered as a Home node with Directory implementation, then all other nodes have to send the request message to the root home node for any cache memory references. This will yield a bottleneck at the Home node and also requiring more number of messages as well. This results with considerable network band width while implementing coherency. A alternative approach is splitting up the Directory in to 3 separate Directory at the nodes “a”, “b” and “d” and resulting with 3 Home nodes. This will result with considerable less number of messages and also reduced bottleneck problems compared to earlier case. Since all computations originating at the nodes “a”, “b” and “d” happen to be local memory reference and hence doesn’t require message exchanges unless the memory reference is outside to the node. Since message handling is shared by 3 different Home nodes, bottleneck problem also eliminated. Designers need to identify the Home nodes appropriately, such that data block happen to be resident to local sites by adopting the concept of locality of references.

Conclusion

The directory-based cache coherence protocol is a scalable approach compared with snooping-based protocol. It avoids broadcasts by storing information about the status of the cache line in a directory and use point-to-point message communication. However, the naive implementation of directory-based cache coherence has much storage overhead, which limits its performance. With Limited Pointer scheme, they replaced the vector with several pointers,

which are log n bit fields that encode the unique identities of those caches containing the data block. With this approach it is possible to have the directory entry with at least three pointers for most large-scale systems, and keeping the memory overhead much lesser than traditional directory schemes. Similar to the limited pointers directories, Dynamic Pointer Allocation Directory scheme uses pointers that contain the unique identities of those caches containing the data. The dynamic pointer allocation directory adds less storage to each data block than a standard limited pointers directory with several pointers per entry. This scheme has resulted with good storage efficiency even in the presence of large caches. Sparse Directory Scheme will simply maintain a small lookup table storing the head of the list for cached lines and can reduce the space overhead dramatically. Here we have some additional pointers in each node's cache, of which the size is proportional to the cache size. However when writing data it needs to iterate through the list and may result with some latency factor. Techniques like Intervention forwarding and Request Forwarding will reduce the total number of message exchanges required while implementing the Cache Coherency and hence limit the network bandwidth. Concept of Localization of Data in Distributed application would reduce the total number of message exchanges required while implementing the Cache Coherency. Localization approach will also reduce the bottleneck problem at central Home Node.

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